

67. Where is Gaia?

GAIA orbits around the Sun–Earth Lagrange point L2, about 1.5 million km from Earth. In this essay, I will outline what L2 is, why it’s special, and why a number of science missions observing deep space (including the James Webb Space Telescope) are positioned there.

I will also describe the substantial effort that is going on, within the Gaia Data Processing and Analysis Consortium, to track with high accuracy its position and its motion around this Lagrange point.

THE LAGRANGE POINTS are the location of gravitational equilibrium for small-mass objects (in our case, Gaia) under the influence of two massive bodies (in our case, the Sun and Earth). At the Lagrange points, the gravitational forces of the two large bodies and the centrifugal force balance each other, leaving small objects placed at the Lagrange points in equilibrium.

There are five such points, known as L1 to L5, all in the orbit plane of any two large orbiting bodies, for example the Sun–Earth system (also in the Earth–Moon system). L1–L3 are on the line through the centres of the two large bodies, and were discovered by Leonhard Euler in 1765.

L4 and L5 form equilateral triangles with the centres of the two large bodies, and were discovered by Joseph-Louis Lagrange, 7 years later, in 1882. Many of our solar system planets have ‘trojan’ asteroids gathered around their L4 and L5 points, with Jupiter hosting thousands!

Strictly, the colinear Lagrange points are in ‘unstable’ equilibrium, and satellites will slowly drift away from them. Detailed mathematical treatment shows that there are nevertheless families of quasi-periodic orbits around L2: ‘halo’ type, and ‘Lissajous’ type. The details need not concern us here, other than to note that small orbit adjustments are occasionally required to keep a satellite at L2 in its intended location.

VARIOUS SATELLITES have been placed at the L1 and L2 points of the Sun–Earth system, L1 being attractive when observing the Sun (e.g. ISEE–3 in the 1970s, SOHO in the 1990s), and L2 for observing deep space.

L2, of relevance for Gaia, lies on the line through the Sun and Earth, about 1.5 million km beyond the Earth (and Moon). Here, the gravitational forces of the Sun and Earth balance the centrifugal force on a body at L2, whose orbital period then matches the Earth’s.

The L2 orbit offers important advantages: amongst them, it provides a stable thermal environment, stable perturbing torques, and observations free from Earth or Moon occultations. Only small and infrequent adjustments are needed to maintain the satellite’s location.

The first mission to exploit L2 was NASA’s WMAP (microwave background) in 2001. It was followed by NASA’s WIND (2003), ESA’s Herschel and Planck observatories (2009), and China’s Chang’e 2 (2011). Satellites currently stationed there include Gaia (since 2013), and JWST (since 2022). Others are planned, including ESA’s Euclid, PLATO, and ARIEL, as well as NASA’s WFIRST.

THIS ORBIT for Gaia was optimised and selected as part of the Concept & Technology Study (ESA 2000), the choice influencing many aspects of the satellite design. Along with numerous advantages, summarised in the table, L2 was fully compatible with the baseline Ariane 5 (and actual Soyuz) launch. Its major disadvantage is for communications, complicating both ground-station visibility and telemetry rate considerations.

Parameter	Low Earth	L4/L5	L2	Geo
Thermal environment	–	*	***	–
Radiation environment	**	***	***	–
Occultations	–	*	***	*
Eclipse avoidance	–	**	***	*
Dynamic environment	–	**	***	**
Injection Δv	***	***	***	**
Maintenance Δv	–	***	***	***
Communications	**	*	**	***
Launch mass	***	**	***	*
Transfer duration	***	**	*	***
Operations	**	**	**	***
Ground facilities	***	***	***	***
Lifetime	*	***	***	*
Overall complexity/cost	–	*	***	*
Recommendation	reject	reject	baseline	reject

DELIVERED TO its L2 location, a 6 month journey after its launch in December 2013, and slowed to its final location by on-board thrusters, the satellite's position and velocity have to be monitored from the ground, so that it can be 'nudged' occasionally, again by its on-board thrusters, so as to remain more-or-less at this L2 location. This orbital adjustment is a common requirement for all satellites operating at the Lagrange points.

But Gaia has another very specific (and particularly demanding) requirement concerning our detailed knowledge of its position, and its velocity, in space.

DETERMINATION of stellar distances with Gaia (based on Earth's orbital motion around the Sun) must more strictly be derived from the *satellite's* distance from the Sun. The latter can be broken down into the Sun-Earth and Earth-satellite displacement vectors.

It turns out that the Earth's orbit is known well enough to account for the former, while the latter must be known to an accuracy of better than about 150 km. But when considering the observations of solar system objects with Gaia, e.g. the main belt asteroids, the satellite position must be known to better than about 150 m!

Similar considerations apply to knowledge of Gaia's velocity with respect to the solar system barycentre (centre of mass), necessary to account for the effect of stellar aberration due to the observer's motion combined with the velocity of light. A full (general relativistic) treatment shows that Gaia's barycentric velocity must be known, at all times, to a demanding 1.5–2.5 mm per sec.

Neither of these exacting requirements, on the knowledge of Gaia's instantaneous position and velocity, can be achieved by the more standard techniques of satellite radar ranging or Doppler measurements.

The more accurate Delta Differential One-way Ranging (Delta-DOR) can contribute, and is used regularly by the Gaia operations team at ESOC (Darmstadt). In this technique, radio signals from the spacecraft are received by two widely separated deep-space optimised ground stations on Earth, and the difference in the signal arrival times is measured.

The timing differences must be adjusted to account for varying delays due to the Earth's atmosphere. This is in turn obtained by simultaneously tracking the signals from radio-emitting quasars nearby on the sky.

But the method requires two ground stations (and competition for their use is intense), and data transmission from Gaia must be suspended during execution.

THE ACCURATE RECONSTRUCTION of Gaia's orbit is therefore supplemented by a dedicated 'ground-based optical tracking' campaign (GBOT), led by Martin Altmann of the Centre for Astronomy (ZAH/ARI) of Heidelberg University. The group comprises a dozen people from Heidelberg and the Paris Observatory, the latter hosting the GBOT data centre.

The group coordinates and reduces astrometric data obtained by tracking the satellite (at an accuracy of about 20 milli-arcsec with respect to the International Celestial Reference Frame) with a number of 2-m class optical telescopes (Altmann 2018; Bouquillon et al. 2018).

The telescopes currently used are the 2.6-m ESO VLT Survey Telescope (VST) on Cerro Paranal in Chile, the 2-m Liverpool Telescope at the Roque de los Muchachos Observatory on La Palma, and telescopes of the Las Cumbres Observatory in Hawaii and Australia.

The task is a challenging one: Gaia is faint (around 21 mag), and relatively fast moving, with an apparent angular motion on the sky of about 0.04 arcsec per second. This has required carefully maximising the resulting positional accuracy (Bouquillon et al. 2017).

In practice, the flight dynamics team at ESOC provides weekly updates of Gaia's geocentric ephemerides. The GBOT group uses these to provide sky charts of Gaia for each telescope location. The telescope teams use these to track the satellite via 10–20 sky images. These are processed by the GBOT group which returns all measurements to ESOC to create an improved Gaia orbit.

The final result is that ESOC creates two orbit files: ORB1 being a weekly update based on ESOC's own Delta-DOR tracking, and ORB2 being a more-or-less annual improved solution including both the Delta-DOR and GBOT measurements, which is then used for the subsequent Astrometric Global Iterative Solution.

THERE IS AN interesting and valuable by-product of the GBOT observations. Since the observations are made near to the ecliptic plane, and essentially at opposition (i.e. directly 'away' from the Sun, being a direction not observable by Gaia), main belt asteroids are frequent interlopers in the telescope's field of view. They are also at their brightest, which facilitates their detection, as well determination of their absolute magnitude.

Consequently, a spin-off GBOT 'asteroid discovery programme' has been active since the beginning of 2015. All their discoveries are sent to the Minor Planet Center for collation, and thereafter for further follow-up by observers world-wide (e.g. Carry et al. 2021).

The daily tally from VST alone amounts to some 10–80 objects, around half of them new. As of January 2022, the GBOT project reports that a total of 43 670 asteroids have been observed, 18 532 of them new.